

LED-BASED DIFFERENTIAL SPECTRAL RESPONSIVITY MEASUREMENTS OF PV MODULES

Hendrik Sträter¹, Stefan Riechelmann¹, Frank Neuberger² and Stefan Winter¹

¹Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), Bundesallee 100, 38116 Braunschweig, Germany

²Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems (ISE), Heidenhofstraße 2, 79110 Freiburg, Germany

ABSTRACT: Spectral responsivity (SR) measurements are a powerful technique to measure the opto-electronic properties of photovoltaic devices like solar cells or PV modules. Although the SR determination of solar cells is a common and established technique for many years, much more effort must be taken to determine the SR of PV modules due to their size. Significantly larger and more complex solar simulator must be used, which led to a variety of different measurement techniques, each with its own disadvantages. In this work we present SR and linearity measurements performed with an LED-based solar simulator, which is capable of measuring the SR of a whole PV module within a reasonable amount of time. The principal solar simulator characteristics with its advantages and challenges are presented, including the properties of the emitted spectrum and the homogeneity of the resulting light field. The evaluation of our method, which is performed at conditions close to standard test conditions (STC) and bears characteristics of a differential spectral responsivity (DSR), is presented and demonstrated on different silicon-based and thin film PV modules, respectively. With the ability to tune the spectral irradiance gradually while maintaining an AM1.5g-like spectrum, linearity measurements of the short-circuit current of PV modules have been performed and are presented as well.

Keywords: Spectral Response, LED, PV Modules, Solar Simulator, DSR

1 INTRODUCTION

The spectral responsivity (SR), or quantum efficiency, is an important opto-electronic property of photovoltaic devices. Not only is it the base for the best estimation of the short-circuit current I_{sc} , but also a powerful technique for failure analysis and research-driven improvement, respectively. Due to the possibility to measure the current generated at different depths within the solar cell much can be learnt from the layers and interfaces within a solar cell.

The determination of the SR of solar cells is quite established for several years and defined in the international standard IEC 60904-8 [1]. Common methods for the determination of the SR of a PV module include:

- Large Xenon flasher illumination of the whole PV module. The wavelength dependence is guaranteed by use of absorbing filters, but often no bias illumination is applied neglecting linearity effects and measuring not at STC.
- Monochromator based modulated illumination with application of bias-light for a single cell within the module. Here it is assumed that all cells have the same SR hence neglecting the interaction of multiple solar cells. Nonetheless, a high number of supporting points with small spectral width can be realized.

Due to their significantly larger size and the need for significantly larger or more complex solar simulators, the SR determination for PV modules is more challenging, and up to now there is no common method for the determination of the SR of modules. With the recent improvements in the LED technology, solar cell characterization using LEDs is already in use and even SR measurements of solar cells have been demonstrated [2].

The advantages of an LED-based simulator compared to the use of absorbing filters or a Xenon flasher are:

- An almost arbitrarily adjustable, spikeless spectrum, including the AM1.x reference spectra, at different irradiance levels.
- Arbitrary long and stable flashes up to steady-state illumination. This is helpful especially for PV devices with noticeable hysteresis.
- Superior durability compared to Xenon lamps.

With the full control over the emitted spectrum, a good match of the AM1.5g spectrum as defined by international standard IEC 60904-3 [3] can be realized without the typical spikes of a Xenon-based system. In addition, non-standard spectra can be easily simulated and allow for an energy rating with nearly arbitrary spectral properties of the irradiance regarding the irradiance and spectral shape.

In our publication, we present DSR measurements of PV modules performed with an LED-based solar simulator designed for PV modules with a size up to 200 cm × 100 cm. This is about the size of a commercially available 72-cell silicon PV module. The emitted light field is of rectangular shape and generated by about 16.000 LED that are focused by micro lenses to the measurement plane. In total, 18 different LED colors are covering the spectral range from 360 nm to 1100 nm. The emitted effective irradiance reaches to up to 1200 W/m² with a pulse duration from a few ms up steady-state conditions over several hours. Each LED color channel can be tuned individually within its limitations. Due to technical reasons, the maximum emitted irradiance of different LED colors varies significantly, and the emitted irradiance depends non-linear from the set LED current.

The size of the active area of the slightly curved solar simulator is about 350 cm × 230 cm and it illuminates a measurement plane of 200 cm × 100 cm at a distance of 550 cm. The maximum angle of incident (AOI) of the light reaching the measurement plane is about 20° with 80 % emitted from an angle of $AOI < 16^\circ$. More information about the angular distribution of the irradiance can be found in a separate publication [4]. Examined PV modules can be mounted on an x-y-z-φ stage, which allows an exact and reproducible placement of PV modules within the light field.

In our solar simulator, the spectral irradiance of the PV module is not modulated but slightly increased and decreased with respect to an irradiance level predefined by the AM1.5g spectrum at 1000 W/m². The signal used for the evaluation is therefore not a differential signal, but a difference signal recorded with a multimeter, as explained in detail in Section 3.

2 PROPERTIES OF THE SOLAR SIMULATOR

2.1 Properties of the emitted spectrum

The spectrum of the solar simulator has been characterized for each LED channel and for the emulated AM 1.5g spectrum at different irradiances. Calibration of the irradiance with a linear WPVS reference cell [5] as well as measurement of the center wavelengths for each LED channel with a spectroradiometer have been conducted in the center of the light field at the same distance between the PV module and the solar simulator.

The relative spectral deviation (SPD) as a measure for the similarity with the AM1.5g spectrum defined in the international standard IEC 60904-3, is

$$SPD = \frac{\sum_{300nm}^{1200nm} |E_{sim}(\lambda) - E_{ref}(\lambda)| \cdot \Delta\lambda}{\sum_{300nm}^{1200nm} E_{ref} \cdot \Delta\lambda}$$

with E_{ref} the AM1.5g reference spectrum and E_{sim} the spectrum of our solar simulator. The SPD accounts to 24.8 % with almost all wavelength ranges satisfying the A+ criterion set in the revised international standard IEC 60904-9 [6] as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Spectral irradiance of the composed AM1.5g-like spectrum compared to the AM1.5g reference spectrum. The colored areas denote the wavelength regime for the classification of a solar simulator defined by the international standard IEC 60904-9.

Although the emitted spectrum covers a spectral range from 360 nm to 1100 nm, as shown in Fig. 1, for the DSR measurements only the central wavelength can be used as sampling point. This limits the number of sampling points to 18 and the spectral range from 367 nm to 1042 nm. The central wavelength, or center of gravity, is calculated by

$$\lambda_0(I_{LED}) = \frac{\int \lambda \cdot S(\lambda, I_{LED}) d\lambda}{\int S(\lambda, I_{LED}) d\lambda}$$

with $S(\lambda, I_{LED})$ the spectrum of the LED channel for a certain current I_{LED} . Fig. 2 shows the set of LED spectra with significantly different shape and width, as they have predominantly been chosen to emulate the AM1.5g spectrum, not for DSR measurements. Before calculation of λ_0 , all spectra have been dark-current corrected and spectral irradiance and wavelength calibrated, respectively.

Figure 2: Calibrated spectra of all LED channels set to the LED current which is needed to compose a spectrum close to the AM1.5g spectrum.

For physical reasons, the center wavelength λ_0 depends on the temperature of the LED, which is dominated by the current flowing through the pn-junction. This leads to shifts of the center wavelength depending on the used spectral irradiance for each LED channel differently. The wavelength shifts of all LED channels depending on the set current between 10 % and 110 % is shown in Fig. 3 revealing shifts of up to several nm between 10 % and 100 % LED current variation. Although the shift can be neglected for small LED current deviations, a separate measurement of each LED peak with the LED current for a DSR measurement is recommended. The negative shift for LED 7 can be explained with the spectrum composed of at least two peaks.

Figure 3: Center wavelength λ_0 with the FWHM (error bar) for each LED channel with the corresponding center wavelength and FWHM shift per 10 % LED current variation.

2.2 Non-uniformity of the light field

Since the light field is generated by the superposition of 60 individual light fields, the homogeneity in terms of total irradiance is of very high quality. According to the international standard IEC 60904-9, the non-uniformity NU of a photovoltaic device is defined as

$$NU = \left(\frac{E_{max} - E_{min}}{E_{max} + E_{min}} \right) \cdot 100\%$$

with E_{max} and E_{min} the maximum and minimum total irradiance, respectively.

We determined the non-uniformity using a customized 72 cell c-Si PV module, denoted in the following as UniformSun module, with cell size of 156 mm × 156 mm. Each solar cell is equipped with its own temperature sensor and has been calibrated in advance. More information about the customized module can be found in [7].

The measured non-uniformity within the light field of the solar simulator is 1.85 % at an irradiance of 1005 W/m², see Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Non-uniformity of the light field across an area of 200 cm × 100 cm with a mean non-uniformity of < 2 %.

As irradiance dependent measurements reveal, the non-uniformity is constant over a wide irradiance range down to 200 W/m², as shown in Fig. 5. Observed deviations for irradiances < 200 W/m² are caused either by the different threshold currents of the individual LEDs, or by small differences in the SR or linearity of the solar cells within the UniformSun module, respectively. From this we can conclude that the impact of the non-uniformity for linearity measurements is minimal down to 200 W/m² but can and should be corrected for lower irradiances.

Figure 5: Non-uniformity and spectral mismatch of the light field as function of irradiance determined with our UniformSun module.

Since the emitted light of each LED channel is a function of the LED current, the composed spectrum is also likely to change with the irradiance level. Therefore, we also calculated the spectral mismatch between two different WPVS cells. The spectral mismatch according to international standard IEC 60904-7 [8] is defined as:

$$SMM = \frac{\int E_{\text{ref}}(\lambda) s_{\text{ref}}(\lambda) d\lambda \int E_{\text{meas}}(\lambda) s_{\text{dut}}(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int E_{\text{meas}}(\lambda) s_{\text{ref}}(\lambda) d\lambda \int E_{\text{ref}}(\lambda) s_{\text{dut}}(\lambda) d\lambda}$$

Here, E_{meas} and E_{ref} denote the spectrum of the solar simulator devices and the AM1.5g reference spectrum,

respectively. The SR of the PV devices are labeled as s_{dut} (device under test) and s_{ref} for the reference (ref).

2.3 Long- and short-term stability

Although LEDs are known to be fast electrical devices and the built-in spectrometer can record a full spectrum every 2 ms, we recommend waiting at least 200 ms for the irradiance of the solar simulator to regard all transient effects of the device under test and the LEDs. Over the 10 measurements for each center wavelength of the experiments presented in this paper, the short-term stability, here the relative deviation between the minimum and maximum current, accounts to about 0.005 %. Within one measurement with a sampling rate of 1000 Hz and a measurement time of 200 ms, the deviation is about 0.05 %.

More critically is the warm up phase of the solar simulator. Within the first 50 pulses, the current of the PV module decreased by about 0.3 %, so a warm-up phase is mandatory.

3 MEASUREMENTS AND RESULTS

3.1 Measurement procedure

For all measurements we used a linear WPVS solar cell as reference cell, which has been calibrated at a primary calibration facility for solar cells at the PTB [8], as reference cell. The WPVS cell is also placed during the measurement of the PV module within the light field.

To obtain the short-circuit current of the reference cell and the PV module we measured the voltage drop across two calibrated shunt resistors with a two-channel Keithley DMM 7512 digital multimeter.

A temperature correction of all measured currents I_{meas} is applied for each measurement using equation

$$I_{\text{corr}} = I_{\text{meas}}(1 - \alpha(T - 25^\circ\text{C}))$$

with α the temperature coefficient obtained from calibrated measurements of the WPVS reference cell or the PV module, or literature values if no calibrated data were available, respectively. The WPVS cell was thermostated at 25°C with use of a Peltier element. To prevent significant heating of the PV module, the illumination time is only 450 ms with a measuring time of 200 ms after a 200 ms delay minimizing transient effects. Between each measurement there is a 5 s pause to prevent PV module heating. The temperature of the PV module has been measured at the rear side by using an attached PT100 thermoelement, while the WPVS cell has its own temperature sensor.

The temperature corrected DSR is calculated from two adjacent measurements subsequently for each LED channel and its corresponding center wavelength λ_0 with increased (E_1) and decreased (E_2) irradiance for this LED channel compared to the irradiance of the AM1.5g-like spectrum. The residual LED channels are set to their standard values. For a sufficient signal-to-noise ratio, the relative increase and decrease of the LED channel has to be chosen carefully, as it depends on the efficiency of the LED and the SR of the PV.

The center wavelength dependent DSR then calculates to

$$DSR(\lambda_0) = \tilde{s}_{\text{ref}}(\lambda_0) \frac{\Delta I_{\text{dut}}(\lambda_0)}{\Delta I_{\text{ref}}(\lambda_0)}$$

with $\xi_{\text{ref}}(\lambda_0)$ the linear interpolated DSR of the reference cell, and

$$\Delta I(\lambda_0) = I(\lambda_0, E_2) - I(\lambda_0, E_1)$$

the measured current differences between the current measurement with increased and decreased irradiance, for the PV module (dut) and the WPVS cell (ref), respectively.

Our method can be understood as a mixture of a DSR and a spectral responsivity approach conducted without bias-light: Since we use a bias light of about 1000 W/m² during the whole measurement, we keep the module at the designated working point defined by STC and non-linearity effects, e.g. due to non-linear back surface fields or defects within the solar cell, are considered.

Fig. 6 shows a sequence of the measured currents with slightly increased and decreased irradiance. The deviation from the set bias level of about 1000 W/m² is < 0.5 % and most likely caused by the current non-linearity of some LEDs. Optimization parameters for this technique are the illumination time, the modulation between the increased and decreased irradiance and delay between the illumination and the measurement. The deviation from the bias level can be set to a constant value by iteratively adjusting the increased and decreased irradiance.

Figure 6: Increased and decreased I_{sc} (blue squares) for each wavelength with the mean I_{sc} (red line).

3.2 Sample overview

We examined our LED-based DSR measurement technique with PV devices based on various technologies, as listed in Table 1. The WPVS cells have been used as reference devices and for a principal verification of our measurement technique. Not all used WPVS cells are listed. Internally or externally calibrated SR measurements exist for the multi-crystalline (mc) Si modules (samples A, B), the CIGS minimodule (sample E) and all WPVS cells.

Table 1: Overview of tested PV modules and WPVS cells.

Sample	Technology	Size
A	mc-Si	60-cell module
B	mc-Si	60-cell module
C	c-Si	60-cell module
D	CdTe	Thin film module
E	CIGS	Minimodule
F	c-Si	WPVS, standard
G	c-Si	WPVS, NIR enhanced

3.3 Verification

For principal verification of our solar simulator and the

used evaluation method we determined the DSR of a WPVS solar cell with known SR determined with our conventional DSR setup [9]. Wavelength resolution of this SR measurement is 5 nm and the combined measurement uncertainty typically accounts to 0.5 %. Here, the absolute SR and the linearity of the WPVS cells is calculated using the algorithm from Metzdorf [10].

Fig. 7 shows the resulting DSR of a WPVS cell (sample F) with an NIR enhanced WPVS cell (sample G) as reference. We find a very good agreement between the DSR measurement obtained with our LED-based solar simulator and DSR measurement with our conventional setup with deviations of less than 1 % between 400 nm and 1050 nm. Nevertheless, we must acknowledge the center wavelength limitation in the UV and IR near regime.

Figure 7: DSR of a WPVS cell with a WPVS cell as reference. The full lines denote the SR determined with our conventional DSR setup, the dashed line the deviation between both setups for one of the WPVS cells.

3.4 Silicon based PV modules

Mono- or multi-crystalline silicon-based PV modules account for the majority of the solar marked world-wide. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to demonstrate that our solar simulator and our evaluation method can determine the DSR of silicon-based PV modules.

Fig. 8 shows the DSR of two different multi-crystalline silicon PV modules (samples A and B). For both modules he SR has also been measured at the Fraunhofer ISE CalLab for Modules. We find a good agreement between our measurement and the measurement performed at the ISE CalLab.

Figure 8: Normalized DSR of two different mc-Si modules with calibrated SR measurements performed at the Fraunhofer ISE CalLab (full lines). The deviation of both measurements is denoted by the dashed lines.

There are deviations of up to 20 % in the NIR regime for sample B which can be explained by non-linearities of the PV module. This effect cannot be seen for sample A, most likely due to technological differences and thus a lower non-linearity in the NIR wavelength regime.

As shown in Fig. 9, we can identify an increased SR of the mono-crystalline PV module (sample C) in near the UV and in the NIR wavelength regime compared to the multi-crystalline PV module (sample B) This can be explained with technological differences on the front side, e.g. better passivated emitter or anti-reflex coating, and improved rear-side properties, respectively. An additional passivation layer at the rear side leads to an increased back-reflection into the solar cell and a reduced recombination at the Si/metallization interface.

Figure 9: DSR of a multi-crystalline Si-based PV module (sample B) and a multi-crystalline Si-based PV module (sample C) revealing a significant higher SR in the NIR wavelength regime due to an improved rear side SR. Full lines act as guide for the eye.

3.5 Thin film PV modules

Figs. 10 and 11 show the DSR of a CIGS minimodule and a CdTe module. Due to the higher bandgap of the used compound semiconductors, the center wavelength limitation of our solar simulator is less crucial. Especially for the CdTe module with a bandgap of about 1.56 eV our solar simulator covers almost the entire spectral range.

Figure 10: Normalized DSR of a CIGS minimodule (sample E) with the DSR determined with our conventional DSR setup. The black dotted line denotes the SR of the use WPVS cell as reference.

Great care must be taken in choosing an appropriate reference cell, as the broad LED peaks distort the SR curve

at the slopes in the UV and NIR spectral range. Therefore, we used an older WPVS cell with lower SR in the NIR compared to an up-to-date WPVS cell for the CIGS minimodule. For the CdTe module, a filtered cell with a cut-off wavelength of 576 nm was used, although the effect of the chosen WPVS cell is negligible except for the UV-near wavelength regime.

Figure 11: Normalized DSR of a CdTe thin film module (sample D) with either a standard WPVS cell or a filtered WPVS cell as reference revealing a better match in the UV near wavelength regime for the filtered WPVS cell. The dotted lines denote the SR of the used WPVS cells. Full lines act as guide for the eye only.

The DSR results of the thin film modules show that our solar simulator at the present state with the limited wavelength regime is also suited for thin film modules, although we find a higher deviation compared to the measurements on Si-based PV modules.

3.6 Linearity measurements of the I_{sc}

PV devices can show a non-linearity of the I_{sc} , e.g. due to charge carrier dependent field effect layers or defects. To use a PV device as secondary calibration standard, e.g. a WPVS cell, or for power rating calculations, the non-linearity of a PV device should be known or, even better, to proven to be non-existent. Different measures for the linearity coexist, e.g. as slope of a linear fit or as deviation between the minimum and maximum normalized current. In the latest version of the corresponding international standard IEC 60904-10 [11], a PV device is considered as linear if the non-linearity is less than 2 %.

With the ability to change the irradiance gradually by modifying the LED current of each LED channel, linearity measurements are relatively easy to realize. As already shown in Fig. 5, the non-uniformity as well as the spectral mismatch, at least for the examined WPVS cell, is stable down to about 200 W/m². With suited corrections of the spectral mismatch and the non-uniformity, linearity measurements of the I_{sc} are realistic for even lower irradiances. More critical is the choice of the shunt resistor, especially for thin film modules with a high V_{oc} and a comparable low I_{sc} of less than 2 A at 1000 W/m².

Fig. 12 shows a linearity measurement of a WPVS cell compared with the linearity determined with our conventional DSR measurement setup. The relative deviation accounts to less than 0.1 % for an irradiance of more than 200 W/m². The deviation for lower irradiances can be explained by the irradiance dependent spectral mismatch non-uniformity, as the measured current has not been corrected to demonstrate the effect.

Figure 12: Linearity of a WPVS cell compared with a measurement from our conventional DSR setup.

The linearity of two Si-based PV modules is shown in Fig. 13. The c-Si PV module shows a more distinct non-linearity which can be explained with a charge-carrier dependent rear side passivation. Nonetheless, the nonlinearity over the whole irradiance variation accounts to less than 1 %, so both PV modules are considered as linear for the examined irradiance variation.

Figure 13: Linearity of a mc- and a c-Si PV module. Full lines act as guide for the eye.

4 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

We presented the DSR of PV modules of different technologies determined with an LED-based solar simulator. With the ability to define a spectrum close to the AM1.5g spectrum at 1000 W/m², we find a good agreement with reference measurements, which are available to us. With the current LED channel configuration and limitations regarding the center wavelengths used for the DSR determination, our solar simulator performs better for thin film modules based on semiconductors with higher band gaps as multi or monocrystalline silicon. Especially for these materials, the longer flash duration is beneficial to avoid hysteresis.

As the center wavelength of each LED channel is a function of the LED current, the center wavelength is prone to spectral shifts. We recommend either to use a look-up table of the LED current dependent center wavelength or, if changes of the photon budget between multiple measurements are likely, to measure the center wavelengths before or after the DSR measurement.

Great care in characterizing the solar simulator must be taken to consider the irradiance dependent spectral

mismatch and non-uniformity of the light field, which are more severe compared to filter- or monochromator based solar simulators.

Since the international standard IEC 60904-10 does not yet cover linearity measurements with a light source, for which the irradiance is changed by tuning the current, more experiments and experience are needed to ensure that an LED-based solar simulator is indeed an appropriate measurement technique for linearity measurements.

Prospective improvements of our LED-based DSR measurement include more central-wavelengths, especially in the UV and NIR range, and a decreased non-uniformity of the light field of < 1 %. After installation of an additional LED-based rear-side illumination with multiple LED colors, we will be capable of measuring bifacial PV modules under both-sided illumination.

Although certain concerns over the spectral width of LED spectra exists, our results show that with an appropriate reference cell, in our case a WPVS cell, a good agreement with calibrated measurement from another calibration institute can be obtained without additional corrections aiming on the spectral width of the LED spectrum. Nonetheless, more comparisons of different SR measurement techniques and PV device technologies are necessary and therefore planned in the future.

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